

Job Experiences of the Municipal Drug Enforcement Unit at Pasuquin, Ilocos Norte

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APPROVAL SHEET

This thesis entitled “**Job Experiences of the Municipal Drug Enforcement at Pasuquin, Ilocos Norte**” prepared and submitted by Aguillon, Ashley Nicole, Balabala, Mark Kevin, Calapao, Dianne Stefhanie, Fermin, Kate Charise, Lagundino, Jan Marck Kristien, Malacas, John Miler, Pasua, John Milnard, Sacsac, John Fermar, and Salvatera, Blessie Joyas partial fulfillment of the requirements for the course Criminological Research and Statistics has been examined and is recommended for acceptance and approval for oral defense.

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The Researchers

DEDICATION

This study is dedicated to their parents who always there extending their hands with patience, understanding and for financial and moral support.

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ABSTRACT

This study was undertaken to discover the Job Experiences of Police Officers under Municipal Drug Enforcement Unit in implementing “Comprehensive Dangerous Drug Act of 2002” (RA 9165). The Case Study as part of the qualitative research method was used in this study to explore the job experiences of the police officers involved in the implementation of drug operations. The respondents were chosen by means of Purposeful sampling which covered four (4) respondents.

The following conclusions where pedagogical implications were drawn. The results found seven themes of the job experiences by the Police Officers under Municipal Drug Enforcement Unit of Pasuquin, Ilocos Norte in implementing “Comprehensive Dangerous Drugs Act of 2002” (RA 9165) which were divided in to three sections to make it more comprehensive. The study covers the different job experiences which are challenging, compromised personal and family security, and thrilling respectively. As to problems encountered by the police officers in conducting operation which resulted impediment of body worn camera and refuse to witness. The strategies utilized by the Police Officers which found to be compartmentalization and Balay Silangan respectively.

This study would open up the consciousness of higher authorities towards positive and negative job experiences of their personnel’s. The study may serve as an assessment for them to evaluate whether their unit needs to be improved regarding on different coping mechanisms to overcome the difficulties brought by the implementation of the Comprehensive Dangerous Drugs Act of 2002 (RA 9165).

Keywords:- Job Experiences, Dangerous Drugs, Challenging, Compromised Personal and Family Security, Thrilling, Impediment, Refuse, Compartmentalization.

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CHAPTER ONE

THE PROBLEM AND ITS SETTINGS

A. Introduction

Choose a job you love and you will never have to work a day in your life. “Confucius” The PNP shall enforce the law, prevent and control crimes, maintain peace and order, and ensure public safety and internal security with the active support of the community.

According to Jacob (2011), The Philippine National Police (PNP) is continuing efforts to improve delivery of basic police services through a more effective crime prevention program anchored upon police community relationships. Several programs had been implemented by the PNP with the end on view of attaining better peace and order situation in communities. Police Administration has been as the management of police organization, which is all about the work of the police officer or the utilization of talents to coordinate an effort and manage resources. The role of a police administrator is to apply their individual initiative and skills necessary for the performance of the actual police roles and responsibilities. (Ralph Celino)

Pasquin is one of the largest municipalities in the province of Ilocos Norte. Different drug operations were also conducted such as checkpoint, police response, buy-bust, hot pursuit, and warrant of arrest. The municipal drug enforcement unit in the municipality continuously keep an eye on their war on drugs to be included in the 347 villages declared drug-cleared in the province of Ilocos Norte. The researcher decided to conduct this study to gain knowledge and evaluate the job experiences of the Police officers under the municipal drug enforcement unit. The study aims to provide updated information on how the job experiences of the Police officers plays a vital role in their service for the implementation of the Comprehensive Dangerous Drugs Act of 2002 (RA 9165).

B. Background of the Study

Illegal drug cases have been one of the major problems not only in our country but globally. Through the continuous battle of the Philippine National Police with the illegal drug related activities in the country, there were 41.5 thousand reported cases involving illegal drugs in the Philippines, majority of which were reported by the National Capital Region's (NCR) regional police office. Reported cases of illegal drugs in the region reached around 12.4 thousand. 943 of which were from Region I. With the intensified drug enforcement in the country has positive impact in cities and provinces. In the 2021 recent news, Ilocos Norte Philippine Drug Enforcement (PDEA) declared that 347 villages in the province are cleared from illegal drugs (Philippine News Agency, 2021).

A study on assessed the performance of the Philippine National Police in their implementation of anti-illegal drug program discussed the professional profile of the PNP, its 17 level of implementation of the anti-illegal drugs prevention program, the status of performance on supply reduction and demand reduction and the problems encountered by the PNP and how serious these are. The study shows that, 1) they are highly educated, lower rank officers, relatively young in service and less trained in drug prevention program, 2) The level of implementation of the anti-illegal Drugs Prevention Program on information and education is least implemented while partnership with the Local Government Units on policy formulation on a drug free community is moderately implemented, 3) The status of performance on supply reduction and demand reduction is fair and 4) Problems encountered by the PNP are moderately serious (Manzano, 2011).

This study was conducted because there were no studies about the work experiences of police officers, and previous studies only focused on the performance on the job and the difficulties encountered when carrying out anti-drug operations.

It will be a great opportunity and a solid foundation for aspiring criminologists who want to work for the Philippine National Police to learn about the work experiences, challenges, and coping mechanisms of police officers assigned to the Drug Enforcement Unit in enforcing Republic Act No. 9165. To comprehend the challenges, they might encounter as well as the risks involved in addressing the illegal drug problem in our nation.

Indeed, future criminologists will be able to learn more about the experiences police officers have had while working drug operations. Researchers will be able to suggest initiatives or concepts to be developed to increase the efficiency in resolving drug-related crimes as a result of this research.

C. Statement of the Problem

The study evaluated the job experiences by the Police Officers under Municipal Drug Enforcement Unit of Pasuquin in implementing “Comprehensive Dangerous Drugs Act of 2002” (RA 9165).

Specifically, in this regard the researcher seeks to answer the following questions:

- What are the different job experiences of the Police officers in implementing “Comprehensive Dangerous Drugs Act of 2002” (RA 9165)?
- What are the problems encountered by the police officers during the conduct of Drug Operations?
- What are the strategies utilized by the police officers under the Municipal Drug Enforcement Unit in implementing “Comprehensive Dangerous Drugs Act of 2002” (RA 9165) at PMPS?
- What is the action plan to be made in order to improve the implementation of RA 9165?

D. Theoretical Framework

The following two (2) theories are applied to support the objectives of the study.

E. Experiential Learning Theory

The Experiential learning involves learning from experience. This theory was proposed by psychologist David Kolb in 1987 who was influenced by the work of other theorists. This theory defined as "the process whereby knowledge is created through the transformation of experience. Knowledge results from the combinations of grasping and transforming the experience."

The relationship between experiential learning theory and this study signifies the important circumstances that involves learning from experiences in which humans follow the same process of reflecting, and acting on daily challenges as ELT advises, whether openly or implicitly. In this study, police officers' experiences are the initial phase in the ELT model. They reflect and reassess their conduct during the operation, which may aid in their journey of self-change. The final phase is for them to put what they've learnt and reflected on during their operations. Thus, this theory asserts that first-hand experiences of police officers in learning and reflecting on their previous acts. This theory can be used to research and analyze the job experiences of police officers' in implementing RA 9165 of this study.

F. Competence Motivation Theory

The Competence Motivation Theory involves that experience a belief in their competence motivation. The theory was proposed by Robert W. White and Susan Harter in 1970. According to them, this theory is the centers on the idea that people are driven to engage in activities to develop or demonstrate their skills. If someone successfully performs a challenging task and receives praise from family or peers for it, then they will experience a belief in their competence in that achievement domain-physical, cognitive or social. Success in that domain will help them recognize that they can control their performance. High perceptions of competence and control create feelings of pleasure that maintain or lead to an increase in competence motivation.

The connection of this theory and the study is the involvement of experience belief in their competence motivation. In this study, police officers' productivity and motivation are important in any organization especially in police agencies wherein police officers have a lot of freedom and discretion and often are unsupervised for many hours of the workday. The individual level of commitment and desire to serve the noble and ethical cause help guide officers' productivity and motivation on the job. Therefore, this theory and the study indicate that on the part of the police officers' varied job experiences, problems that occur, and coping mechanisms on the various strategies that were implemented, where in after the implementation it will be the time to understand if the outcome of that operation involves their desire to be competent and motivated as well.

G. Job Performance Theory

Job Performance Theory was proposed by Campbell (1990). Performance was defined by Campbell as actions or behaviors that are relevant to the organization's goals and that can be assessed in terms of the degree to which they contribute to those goals. It is possible to distinguish between these behaviors and effectiveness, which is the influence that behaviors have on results. He also views technical skill performance as the foundation of a person's job-specific task proficiency.

Consider a few of the presumptions that underlie the concept of performance when defining it (Motowidlo, Borman, & Schmit, 1997). Performance is a behavioral construct. The authors make a distinction between performance and performance results. The first refers to a set of behaviors that can have either a positive or negative impact on organizational effectiveness while the second refers to states that are altered by individual behavior. Performance outcomes are impacted by variables outside of an individual's control.

This theory and this study's relationship signifies its important circumstances which explains that employees with a higher job satisfaction score have higher job performance. That the performance of a person throughout a work or job will be resulted to the one's behavior or their organization.

H. Conceptual Framework

The Input-Process-Output (IPO) Model is a useful graph that lists the inputs, outputs, and steps needed to convert inputs into outputs. The IPO model represents the summary of various related articles that explains the processes involved. This directs the researcher in coming-up with a series of action required in the entire duration of the given educational research. It considers the insights of the other researchers and their findings on the subject of their research. (Canonizado, I., 2020).

The figure showed below is the paradigm of the study which represents how the researchers conducted the study, which serves as a basis for the proposed action plans. The researchers used IPO model to wherein the Input contains the research problem of the study. The process of the study composed of four (4) which was the research method used, the instruments and procedure used. The output of the study is the action plans on how the police officers will improve the implementation of RA 9165, and way to suppress the problem encountered during the drug operation.

Fig. 1: Research Paradigm

I. Significance of the Study

Subsequent to the study conducted on exploring and identifying the job experiences of Police Officers under Municipal Drug Enforcement Unit in implementing “Comprehensive Dangerous Drugs Act of 2002” (RA 9165) at Pasuquin, Ilocos Norte. The study’s findings used as a foundation of the following:

- **Philippine Drug Enforcement Unit.** The study would open up their consciousness towards positive and negative job experiences of their personnel’s. This may bring awareness over the challenges and struggles they lived. The study may serve as an assessment for them to evaluate whether their unit needs to be improved regarding on different coping mechanisms to overcome the difficulties brought by the implementation of the Comprehensive Dangerous Drugs Act of 2002 (RA 9165).
- **Future Police Officers.** They may use this study to have knowledge on what are the Job Experiences of the police officers in implementing RA 9165 and how officers perform their duties and responsibilities in the different Drug operations.
- **The Community.** This study will give them awareness about job experiences and problems occur of police officers in implementing RA 9165 to prevent them to a higher possibility in engaging illegal activities.
- **Future Researchers.** The study would bring awareness about challenges as well as the positive impact that come along with that may use this study to have knowledge on what are the Job Experiences of the police officers in implementing RA 9165. It would also encourage them to make further studies about the research topic for them to yield more accurate and reliable results.

J. Scope and Limitations

The scope of the study comprised the job experiences of the Municipal Drug Enforcement Unit atPasuquin Municipal Police Station. Specifically, to identify the different job experiences, to know the problems encountered during drug operation, the strategies utilized to implement the RA 9165, and the action plans to improve the implementation and ways to suppress the problems occur in drug operation. The study is only limited on the job experiences of the Municipal Drug Enforcement Unit atPasuquin Municipal Police Station. It covers 4 selected police officers who have actually experienced drug operations.

This study was conducted in the first semester AY 2022-2023.

K. Definition of Terms

For clarification, the following definitions apply to the terms that were used in the study.

- **Buy-Bust.** All warrantless arrest, search, and seizures to be undertaken by PNP member/anti-drug units shall be in accordance with Section 5, paragraphs (a) and (b), Rule 113, Section 13, Rule 126 of the Rules of Court, respectively and relevant Supreme Court Decisions.
- **Challenging.** Challenging is arousing competitive interest, thought, or action. It is also offering a challenge and testing one's ability, endurance, etc.
- **Compromised.** This refers to the security of the police officers and their families wherein they are feeling threaten.
- **Drug Enforcement Officer.** This refers to the implementing bodies of RA 9165 who are responsible for implementing laws and regulation governing narcotics and controlled substances.
- **Impediment.** This refers to the problems of the body worn camera that the police officers used in conducting operations.
- **Job Experience.** Any experience that a person gains while working in a specific field or occupation. Also, it means a paid work activity that provides a participant with an opportunity to acquire the general skills, training, and knowledge.
- **Law Enforcement.** The activity of some members of government who act in an organized manner to enforce the law by discovering, deterring, or punishing people who violate the rules and norms governing that society.
- **Philippine Drug Enforcement Agency.** The agency is tasked with the enforcement of the penal and regulatory of Republic Act No. 9165, otherwise known as the Comprehensive Dangerous Drugs Act of 2002.
- **Philippine National Police (PNP).** The national police force of the Republic of the Philippines. It is both a national and a local police force in that it provides all law enforcement services throughout the Philippines.
- **Refuse.** This refers to the problems to the witnesses especially the barangay officials in coordinating with the police officers during operation.
- **Republic Act No. 9165.** Otherwise known as the Comprehensive Dangerous Drugs Act of 2002, provides that: "the State needs to enhance further the efficacy of the law against dangerous drugs, it being, one of today's more serious social ills.
- **Thrilling.** Causing the feeling of a sudden excitement.

CHAPTER TWO

REVIEW RELATED LITERATURES AND STUDIES

This chapter includes articles, unpublished thesis/dissertations related to the topic were reviewed by the researchers to guide them in conceptualizing and conducting the study. The concepts taken from these reference materials are presented in this chapter.

A. Policing

In the literature over the last decade, policing has been widely discussed as a stressful occupation in comparison to other professions. According to Campbell and Nobel 2009; Vuorensyrjä and MalkiaVuorensyrjä and Mälkiä 2011, because of the officers' exposure to a variety of acute and chronic stressful events at work, it has been identified as one of the most demanding and stressful occupations in the world (Lieberman et al. 2002; Magnavita and Garbarino 2013; Paton et al. 2009). As a result, police officers are more likely to suffer from physical and mental illnesses, such as impaired psychosocial wellbeing and physical ill-health (Garbarino, Cuomo, Chiorri, and MagnavitaGarbarino et al. 2013; Lucas, Weidner, and Janisse Lucas et al. 2012), self-harm, and poor functioning (Volanti et al. 2016).

B. Legal Basis in Republic Act 9165

SECTION 21. Custody and Disposition of Confiscated, Seized, and/or Surrendered Dangerous Drugs, Plant Sources of Dangerous Drugs, Controlled Precursors and Essential Chemicals, Instruments/Paraphernalia and/or Laboratory Equipment. – The PDEA shall take charge and have custody of all dangerous drugs, plant sources of dangerous drugs, controlled precursors and essential chemicals, as well as instruments/paraphernalia and/or laboratory equipment so confiscated, seized and/or surrendered, for proper disposition in the following manner:

- The apprehending team having initial custody and control of the drugs shall, immediately after seizure and confiscation, physically inventory and photograph the same in the presence of the accused or the person/s from whom such items were confiscated and/or seized, or his/her representative or counsel, a representative from the media and the Department of Justice, and any elected public official who shall be required to sign the copies of the inventory and be given a copy thereof.

PNP Manual on Anti-Illegal Drugs Operation and Investigation.

- **RULE III- SPECIFIC RULES AND PROCEDURES**– This rule covers the procedures in any planned or unplanned anti-illegal drug operation and investigation:

- I – PLANNED OPERATIONS

- **Section 19. Buy-Bust Operation**- All warrantless arrest, search, and seizures to be undertaken by PNP member/anti-drug units shall be in accordance with Section 5, paragraphs (a) and (b), Rule 113, Section 13, Rule 126 of the Rules of Court, respectively and relevant Supreme Court Decisions.

- **PRIOR TO BUY-BUST**

- The Team Leader shall see to it that prior reports have been submitted which may include but not limited to the following classified reports:
 - ✓ Summary of Information of the target/s
 - ✓ Special Reports
 - ✓ Surveillance Report
 - ✓ Contact meeting report
 - ✓ Development report

- If necessary, a test buy may first be conducted. If there's any, the dangerous drugs purchased shall be photographed, marked, packaged, sealed and submitted to PNP Crime Laboratory for examination. The PNP CRIME LABORATORY shall issue a laboratory result for the purpose.
- Preparation of the buy-bust or boodle money. The "buy-bust" money shall be duly marked or dusted with ultra-violet powder by the PNP Crime Laboratory. It shall be properly photographed, reproduced and/ or recorded indicating the serial numbers and the person who released the money, the officer who received the same and delivered to the PNP Crime Laboratory for dusting. The officer receiving the money shall issue a receipt for the purpose.
- Preparation of the prior coordination with PDEA as far as practicable and the territorial police units.
- Preparation of the Inventory Receipt of Evidence Form for recovered evidence, the Technical Inspection Receipt form for recovered vehicles, and other pro-forma documents needed in the operation.
- Preparation and inspection of the following: Firearms, communication, vehicles, camera and other equipment and documents to be used by the team members.
- The Team Leader shall ensure that he has the contact numbers of the representatives from DOJ, Media and any local elected officials in the area for inventory purposes as required under Section 21, RA 9165.

➤ *BUY-BUST PHASE*

- The poseur-buyer should ensure that the suspect delivers the dangerous drugs or accepts the marked or dusted money before giving the pre-arranged signal for the arrest. In the pre-positioning of the team members, the designated arresting and/or back-up elements should observe the negotiation/transaction between the suspect and the poseur-buyer. The back-up elements should be strategically positioned to secure the area.
- Upon the execution of the pre-arranged signal, the designated arresting officers shall arrest the suspect/s. They shall introduce themselves as police officer to the suspect/s.
- The arresting officers shall inform the arrested suspect/s of his/her CONSTITUTIONAL RIGHTS in a language understandable to him. (I/We are police officers I/we are arresting you for violation of RA 9165.
- After the arrest, the arresting officers shall search the body of the suspect for the recovery of the buy-bust money and/or deadly weapon.
- The seizing officer shall immediately seize and take initial custody of the dangerous drugs.
- The seizing officer shall thereafter conduct the actual physical inventory, place markings and photograph the evidence in the place of operation in the presence of:
 - ✓ The accused or the person/s from whom such items were confiscated and/or seized or his/her representative or counsel;
 - ✓ A representative from the media;
 - ✓ A representative from the Department of Justice; and
 - ✓ Any elected public official (at least Brgy Kagawad) who shall sign, and shall be given copies of the inventory.

C. Rules on the Use of Body-Worn Cameras in the Execution of Warrant No. 21-06-08-Supreme Court

SECTION 3. Use of Body-Worn Cameras During Arrest. At least one body-worn camera and one alternative recording device, or such number as necessary to capture and record the relevant incidents during execution of the warrant shall be worn by members of the team making the arrest by virtue of a warrant. Should a body-worn camera be unavailable, at least two alternative recording devices must be used. The officers having such cameras shall ensure that they are worn in a conspicuous location and in a manner that maximizes their ability to capture a recording of the arrest.

According to the study of Ceniza, G. (2019), He investigated the lived experiences of police officers involved in the implementation of the Philippine National Police anti-drug operation program. According to his study's findings, the PNP organization must provide all necessary facilities and equipment for operations.

Continuous training and seminars should be implemented to improve police officers' skills and capabilities in conducting drug operations.

D. Job Satisfaction

Aziri (2011) argued that job satisfaction represents a feeling that appears as a result of the perception that jobs enable the material and psychological needs. The police officers' psychological condition is to arrest the drug suspect successfully. In Job Performance Theory, explains that employees with a higher job satisfaction score have higher job performance. Such means that the more satisfied people are in their work, the higher job satisfaction they have.

E. Implementation of Body Worn Camera

According to Miller (2014) stated that "Everyone is on their best behavior when the cameras are running. The officers, the public-everyone." Perhaps most importantly, the implementation of body-worn cameras has increased the transparency and accountability of officers. Not only has the technology helped reduce confrontations between the public and officers, it has also reduced conflict between officers.

Similarly, to the statement of Miller (2014). Panel Lena (2021) stated that they have issued a directive to implement Supreme Court (SC) Circular 21-06-08 issued on June 29, 2021, on the "approved rules of the use of body-worn cameras" in the execution of warrants. In addition, he stated that in the case of buy-bust operations, the use of a body camera would be too obvious while an agent makes a transaction. She added that noting the subjects of buy-busts are "very sensitive" and it would be impossible for them not to know if the agent is wearing one.

Juancho Gallarde (2018), he stated that Barangay officials were cautioned against refusing to witness inventories of confiscated illegal drugs during buy-bust operations or conduct of search warrant. He also cited a case in Cebu wherein the entire group of barangay officials was suspended for refusal to witness in an inventory of confiscated illegal drugs and paraphernalia.

In the case of *People v. Sorin* (G.R. No. 212635, March 25, 2015) is instructive. Here, the accused was acquitted because of an irregularity in the buy-bust operations. Specifically, the apprehending officer who seized the sachets from the accused Sorin during the buy-bust operation failed to mark the sachets and, instead, turned them over unmarked to another police officer. The latter officer was the person who marked the sachets of shabu, and who eventually took custody of the confiscated drugs and delivery to the PDEA.

Supreme Court, stated that the fact the sachets of drugs were not marked for inventory in the presence of the apprehending officer who confiscated the drugs is fatal to the cause of the prosecution. "The Court cannot over-emphasize the significance of marking in illegal drugs cases. The marking of the evidence serves to separate the marked evidence from the corpus of all other similar or related evidence from the time they are seized from the accused until they are disposed of at the end of the criminal proceedings, thus, preventing switching, planting, or contamination of evidence."

In conclusion, police are faced with many dangerous and volatile situations where their lives and those of innocent civilians may be at risk. It is quite difficult, for example, to handcuff a suspect who resists. Even two officers may not be able to cuff a resisting suspect. If more than one officer is involved, it may well seem to a civilian bystander that police are acting in a brutal manner. The suspect himself may sustain injuries in the process, which he will later claim were caused by police brutality.

F. Strategies in Drug operation

Their duties are to formulate and implement plans and programs for international cooperation on intelligence and investigation reclusive to drug trafficking and prevention. Coordinate and orchestrate the support and participation of Local Government Units (LGUs) and Non- Governmental Organizations (NGOs) in the anti- drugs campaign down to the barangay level: Recommend the enactment of appropriate

anti- illegal drug laws and issuances; perform such other tasks and functions as the President of the Republic of the Philippine may direct; and coordinate and collaborate with the 1DDB with regard to demand reduction, rehabilitation, education and information programs (Estrada, 1991).

Along et al (2008) recommend that the local government should give adequate budget to the PNP Organization to meet the needs and for them to easily perform their duties. The PNP should also conduct seminar on how to an efficient investigator. And to the community they recommend that they should also be oriented about the problems encountered by the police investigators on crime scene specially the Barangay officials.

Tuot et al., (2017) argued that a sensitive drug control policy is evident to combat drug problems effectively. Research evidence presented in the World Drug Report 2016 indicates that efforts to achieve sustainable development goals and address the world drug problems effectively are complementary and mutually reinforcing. In other words, to address the issues related to the use of illicit drugs, policies need to aim at the overall social, economic and environmental development of communities. However, Werb (2011), suggested that increasing drug law enforcement is unlikely to reduce drug market violence. Instead, the existing evidence indicates that gun violence and high homicide rates may be the inevitable consequences of drug prohibition and that disrupting drug markets can paradoxically increase violence. In this context, drug prohibition has not meaningfully reduced drug supply and an alternative regulatory models may be required if drug supply and drug market violence are meaningfully reduced.

G. The Balay Silangan Reformation Program

Provides intervention for small-time drug offenders who are neither users nor dependents. It includes guidelines that provide for its administrative and operational requirements with corresponding criminal and administrative penalties for its violation and non-implementation. Director General Aaron N. Aquino initiated the program. This is a new approach aimed to address the surge of drug offenders who surrendered and availed of the plea bargain since there was no institutionalized intervention for the Program's intended clients. The Program was adopted by the Dangerous Drugs Board as a Regulation in January 2018.

The primary objective of the Program is to provide a humanitarian alternative to arrest, prosecution, and conviction of small-time drug offenders who are neither drug users nor dependents.

Before Balay Silangan, drug offenders who are non-users/dependents are subjected to arrest, prosecution, and conviction regardless of involvement in the drug trade. As a result, law enforcement units, courts, and jails were overwhelmed. Further, the Supreme Court decision in the case of Estipona vs. Judge Frank Lobrigo allowed drug offenders to avail of plea bargaining. Unfortunately, there were no programs for drug offenders who were granted plea bargains. Treatment and rehabilitation became the "band-aid solution" to these concerns. However, this is an intervention for drug users/dependents and not for other violators of the Drug Law.

The Bataan PNP Office has an initiative aimed to expedite the Barangay Drug Clearing Program (BDCP) by giving intervention to the individuals cited above instead of arresting them. However, this initiative is not institutionalized and is more of a stop-gap measure for the BDCP rather than being a program by itself.

H. Solution and Impact

The Balay Silangan Reformation Program was conceptualized when law enforcement, prosecution, and incarceration was the only course of action to address all drug offenders, both small-time and big time. This is an approach that cannot avoid violence and trauma despite best efforts. This is manifested by the conduct of arrest, filing of charges, and deprivation of liberty of the drug offender.

The “Balay Silangan” brought a transformation by changing the paradigm on how to address small-time drug offenders. This new approach is grounded on compassion by looking at the human side of the drug situation. It considers that its intended clients, small-time drug offenders, are compelled to engage in the illegal drug trade due to lack of legitimate means of livelihood and lack of proper guidance. This innovation takes a course of action that avoids the trauma while providing them with an opportunity for a new life without being subjected to enforcement operations and getting a criminal record. Further, its clients are allowed to reform without being deprived of liberty.

“Balay Silangan” was adopted for implementation. Ever since it has made an impact on the lives of nine hundred forty-eight (948) individuals. Same individuals who would have been subjected to a paradigm with a high probability of violence, trauma, and deprivation of liberty without “Balay Silangan”. With this innovation, these individuals were provided with education, livelihood, and various kinds of support that aims to reintegrate them to society and be able to contribute positively.

I. Related Studies

In the study of Geral L. Ceniza (2019) on “Lived Experiences of the Philippine National Police Anti-Drug Operation Officer”. The study explores the lived experiences of police officers in the implementation of the Philippine National Police anti-drug operation program. It highlights the experiences of the police officers involved in a drug operation and the strategies applied in solving the issues and challenges, including its effect on the personal and official career of the police officers. The study resulted in eight major themes emerging from the experiences of the informants. For the lived experiences of the participants in the conduct of drug operations, the following are the emergent themes: Feeling great when there is a catch, facing tall and hard wall, and being uncooperative. The strategy applied by the informants in solving the issues and challenges came up with the emergent themes: Having police initiative and securing an effective plan, contentment in the working performance, compromised personal and family security, and commendation for the accomplishment were the emergent themes regarding the effect of operation in the personal and professional careers of the participants. The results of study suggest that the PNP organization must provide all the necessary facilities and equipment for the operations. Continuous training and seminar should be initiated to strengthen the skills and capabilities of police officers in conducting drug operations.

Verzosa (2009) in her study on "Personnel Performance of Philippine National Police (PNP) Legazpi." gave following conclusions: 1) The level of performance of the police personnel in Legazpi City under Administrative and Operation Branches is very satisfactory (VS). They are very effective in the performance of their work; 2) there are inadequacies perceived by the police personnel while in the performance of their functions. The major ones are: lack of operational funds inadequate number of office equipment, mobility and firepower, lack of communication equipment and lack of training, schooling and seminars attended.

Hitoris (2005) also conducted an assessment study on the Performance of Police Stations in Albay. The performance of the police stations on their mandated activities which covered police assistance, crime prevention; security and safety, crime resolution, conduct and care for the community, and peace and order were assessed. The study included the problems encountered and recommendations offered to enhance the performance of the police stations. Hitoris study is similar to the present study in terms of its subject matter. The subject matter is on performance of police stations in Albay while the present study focused on the job experiences of municipal drug enforcement unit.

According to the study of Mabida (2011) entitled "The problems encountered by the Philippine National Police in handling human trafficking cases" emphasizing the problems faced by the PNP had considered famished because of the knowledge of the composition of human traffickers. Filing the cases, securing of warrants of arrest and the conduct of interrogations are mostly the problems faced by the Criminal Investigation and Detection Group (CIDG) in regard to investigations. The researcher stated some recommendations that could help the PNP in avoiding problems like "comprehensive Training Program on

the PNP, especially CIDG's anti - trafficking Strategy". Thus, study is related to the present study because it identified the problems encountered by the CIDG in handling human trafficking cases while the present by seeks to identify the problems encountered during operation.

CHAPTER THREE

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This chapter presents and discusses the research method and design that were used in the study; the research population and locale, the sampling procedures, data gathering procedure and treatment of data.

A. Research Method

The study was classified as qualitative research. According to Arora and Stoner (2009), Qualitative research is intended to deeply explore, understand and interpret social phenomena within its natural setting. By using the qualitative research methodology, the researchers collected richer information and more detailed pictures of issues, cases or events.

The researchers used Case study to explore the job experiences of police officers involved in the implementation of drug operations. Yin (1994) explained that a case study is a comprehensive research strategy that deals with situations in which there will be more variables of interest than data points, relies on multiple sources of evidence, with data needing to be converged in a triangulating fashion, and that benefits from the prior development of theoretical propositions to guide data collection and analysis. Case Study was used in speaking with the police officers in-depth and it gives the researchers the opportunity to gain a greater understanding of the subject in hand. The emergent themes and significant statements from the responses were selected and given fundamental meaning.

B. Population and Locale of the Study

There were four respondents in the study from Pasuquin Municipal Police Station who are under the Municipal Drug Enforcement Unit because they are the police officers who have actually experienced drug operations and believed to give the researchers the information needed in the study.

The respondents were chosen by means of Purposeful sampling. Purposive sampling technique, also called judgment sampling, is the deliberate choice of an informant due to the qualities the informant possesses (Bernard, 2002 and Lewis & Sheppard, 2006). It is a non-random technique that does not need underlying theories or a set number of informants. Simply put, the researcher decides what needs to be known and sets out to find people who can and are willing to provide the information by virtue of knowledge or experience. Thereafter, the respondents that were involved in the study had been interviewed and they answered truthfully and with honesty. It is a sampling technique used by qualitative researchers to recruit participants who can provide detailed information about a phenomenon. As a result, the researcher used this method to collect data and information more effectively. It also allows researchers to obtain a sample population that best represents the entire population being studied, ensuring that the sub-group of interest was represented.

C. Research Instrument

The researcher created an interview guide to collect the necessary data for the study. This study used open-ended questions to enable the researcher to collect in-depth information and for the participants to share their experiences freely.

The interview guide is composing of questions about the different job experiences of the police officers in implementing RA 9165; the problem encountered by the police officers during the conduct of drug operations; and the strategies utilized by the police officers under the Municipal Drug Enforcement Unit in implementing RA 9165.

A recorder device (phone) was used during the actual interview to administer questionnaires in order to further clarify the statement of the issue and how to specifically answer it all in order to achieve the study's objective.

D. Data Gathering Procedure

In the conduct of the study, the researcher's follow a specific procedure in order to achieve the study's objectives. First the researchers used the purposeful sampling to identify the research respondents. Second, the researchers sent a letter to the research adviser regarding the approval of the research respondents. Third, the interview guide was checked, validated and approved by the research adviser. Fourth, the researchers drafted letter of request to the Chief of Police and respondents, after that developing of questions that was based on the study's objectives, which they then submit to the researcher adviser for approval. Fifth, with the research adviser's approval, the researcher personally appeared to give the letters to the Chief of Police to conduct the study. Sixth, once the Chief of Police has approved the study, the interview be conducted in accordance with the proper health protocol. Finally, the researchers were retrieved and analyze the data that has been collected.

E. Treatment of Data

The researchers used thematic analysis to identify the common themes of the job experiences of the Police Officers in implementing RA 9165. The data gathered through the method of interview was treated thematically using in-depth analysis and questioning of respondents based on their responses, where the interviewer/researcher also tries to understand their motivation and feelings.

Thematic analysis is a method for analyzing qualitative data that entails searching across a data set to identify, analyze and report repeated patterns. It is a method for analyzing qualitative data that involves searching across a data set to identify, analyze, and report repeated patterns, used by the researcher to collect data (Braun and Clarke 2006). It is a flexible approach to qualitative analysis that enables researchers to generate new insights and concepts derived from data. In thematic analysis is usually applied to a set of texts, such as an interviews or transcript. It goes further into the interpretation and data transformation process.

The data were treated using the following steps:

The themes arrived from the gather data. First step, arrange the gather data in a verbatim way. Step two, setting a proper code from the gather data. Lastly, arrive a theme on the proper code were provided. The findings cannot be measured or judged without the consistency of the collected data; the researchers were broadening their perspective. External validation was provided by how well the results are applicable to other situations.

F. Ethical Consideration

Ethics is important in conducting research and the challenges around conducting research, researchers go to great lengths to protect the dignity and safety of research participants (Silverman, 2009). Several ethics consideration was taken into account to ensure that this study was conducted in an appropriate manner. To comply with ethical considerations in conducting research, all participants provided a written request letter and a verbal consent about the research purpose and process were explained. The participants were voluntarily participated in the study after they were approached by the researchers. Researchers also asked the participants permission to record the interview from them and none of the participants had difficulties with the phone recording of the interviews.

It was further explained to the participants that their information would remain confidential and that the specific content of individual interviews would only be discussed with the research adviser.

At the end of the interviews, both participants and the researchers debriefed by talking about the interview process itself for ensuring that the participants were not left emotionally harmed. Also, researchers gave simple token to the participants as an appreciation for their time and willingness to share their experiences.

CHAPTER FOUR

INTERPRETATION, PRESENTATION AND ANALYSIS OF DATA

This chapter presents, interprets and analyses the data gathered from the study of exploring the job experiences of police officers in implementing RA 9165.

The data revealed a number of themes that captured the opinions of specific officers which are challenging, compromised personal and family security, exciting, impediment of body worn camera, refuse to witness, compartmentalization and Bahay Silangan respectively.

The job experiences of police officers during drug operations were proven to be distinctive. These various experiences were interpreted into the following themes which was discussed below:

➤ *Theme 1: Challenging*

Buy Bust Operation is one of the most dangerous operations conducted by the police because of a shortage or a mistake in the actions of the policemen may cause their life in exchange for it. The challenging part of the job was the following of the Standard Operating Procedure in implementing RA 9165, that in some cases the procedures are not followed due to awareness of some suspects of the marked money. So, they resort in taking photographs of the money's including the docket number and proceed to blotter. They will then defend their course of action in the court to justify the technique they used and prevent it from being dismissed. Police officers have experienced the positive and negative effects of drug operations within their personal and official life. However, these challenges developed their innate desire to demonstrate competence in their performance. According to the competence motivation theory, success or mastery of a task can lead to an overall increase in the perception of one's own competence.

As to participant 1, he explained that,

“Job experiences adudetaadutnaexperience ko ngemianaklattataysignificant'nnga challenging, ti mesa nganaexperience mi idikettay regarding ti mark money.” (P1, Page 1, L. 1-2)

“Tay marked money, there was a time markan mi ngamin jay kwartaidikaslakuma jay 500 ikwamtay initial mo, tay initial mo ICC kumati initial tinaganmo so there was a time ikkan mi ti markings mi idiaginnawat kami jay drugs ken taybayadenidi. Nakita na jay kwartanga adda mark ana idjayngakwanngatikunanakanyaminga “ninay police kayo” ginelnelnataposinbakalnatajkwartataposnagtarayngaisutrasonngahannanagsucceedtay operation min”. (P1, Page 1, L 2-8)*

(Job experiences I do have a lot but I will tell you what was the significant that is challenging, one of my experiences was regarding the mark money.

The marked money, that there were times that we need to mark the money, for example, if the amount is 500 you need to put your initial, like ICC was your initial name. So, there was a time that we put markings, that the suspect and I was exchanging the drugs and money, the suspect notices the money that has marked that the suspect told us “ninayo police kayo”, then the suspect crumpled the money and thrown it away then run immediately.)

He also added that:

“From that time being haankamnganagmarktoney’n, tiubraminket noag buy-bust kamintipimmayan mi kethanmimamarkantaykwartan so tiinkabil mi nukwandijaykwartangausaren mi picturan mi and the at the same time ikwa mi jay blotter idocket mi jay number taykwarta. So dijaynukwatay mark money’n, ti gamin kwanadijaytinagbalinnga debate mi kadijaykwaidjayngamin police operational procedure tiibagbagana jay when conducting a drug buy bust operation money to be use should be marked. Kaya lang kadijaynga experience mi isunganagdibate kami ngaiblotter min with that experience inpaliwanag mi met jay, idinagcourt duty nakuninpaliwanag ko dijaykorte no apay hamiminarkandijaykwarta.” (P1, Page 1, L. 17-28)

(From the time being we did not mark the money, what we did is that, when we conduct buy bust, we are not going to mark the money so we just put the money , were going to use, we took a picture and at the same time we include it in the blotter , we docket the number of the money, so that is already marked money, it became a debate for us, because of the police operational procedure , it stated that when conducting a drug buy bust operation the money to be use should be marked but those thing we experience we debate that we must put in the blotter, with those experience, we explain in the court, when the time duty explained to the court why we did not mark the money used.)

As to the respondent 2, he stated that:

“Different job experiences adanaglalaok which is challenging, adadagitay nag prosper nakaswannai balodnagprobation nag plea bargaining ada met dagitikin couner charge dakamikadagiti planting of evidence.” (P2, P 3, L. 101-103)

(We have different job experiences which makes our job more challenging. We successfully filed a case, some people prospered, detained, probationed and others plead bargaining. Some filed counter-charges against us with intentional planting of evidences.)

Challenging was perceived to be the first job experienced of the police officers in implementing RA 9165 also known as Comprehensive Dangerous Drug Act of 2002. This includes the; non-compliance of marking money and to present, justify in court about the technique. As to the result of the study, researchers found out that police officers experienced challenge during anti-drug operations because of the procedure that was provided in the PNP Manual on Anti-Illegal Drugs Operation and Investigation, Rule 3-Specified Rules and Procedures Section 19, that was not followed accordingly because of the suspect’s awareness. Therefore, to adapt to the challenged faced, the police made use of the certain technique in order for the suspect to not notice any marks on the money.

This is supported in the PNP Manual on Anti-Illegal Drugs Operation and Investigation, Rule 3-Specified Rules and Procedures Section 19, which provided that prior to buy-bust paragraph (c) the buy-bust money shall be duly marked or dusted with ultra-violet powder by the PNP Crime Laboratory.

Undoubtedly, the failure to mark the money properly during a buy-bust operation could lead to the accused's acquittal. In fact, it was decided in the People v. Sorin case before the Supreme Court (G.R. No. 212635, March 25, 2015). In this case, a flaw in the buy-bust procedures led to the accused's acquittal. In particular, the officer who arrested Sorin during the buy-bust operation failed to mark the sachets and instead handed them over to another police officer without marking them. The Supreme Court stated that it was impossible to overstate the importance of marking in cases involving illegal drugs. From the time it is taken from the accused until it is disposed of at the conclusion of the criminal proceedings, the marking of the evidence serves to separate it from the corpus of all other similar or related evidence, preventing switching, planting, or contamination of evidence.

➤ *Theme 2: Compromised Personal and Family Security*

The threat to police officers' personal and family security. Due to the police officers' involvement in the anti-drug operation, there was a threat to them personally and a risk to their family as well. Along with the sense of contentment, they also worry that as they carry out more operations, their enemy count will rise. Additionally, drug operations not only pose a threat to and negatively impact police officers, but also their families' quality of life. Because of the perceived threat that the operation's arrested subject might at any time exact revenge, the police officers' social lives and those of their families are compromised. A potential threat to the safety of police officers' homes and families. There was a risk to the police officers' safety as well as the safety of their families because of their participation in the anti-drug operation. They are both content and concerned that as they conduct more operations, the number of their enemies would increase. The quality of life for police officers' families is also adversely affected by narcotics operations, which also present a threat to and harm police officers. The police officers' own lives as well as those of their families are at risk due to the perception that the operation's arrested subject may at any point take revenge.

As to participant 2, he stated that:

“Tiriknasyempreada met tay time ngaagdanagak most specially nu dagiti. mapan mi iseservanti search warrant ketdagitay adda, adda kaya nangamabalinna met dangrantifamily'kisuti mesa panpanunutekidiagconconduct kami.” (P2, Page 4, L.117-119)

(I felt in danger especially if those suspects are having such power, power that they may commit danger to my family that is one on my mind when conducting such operation.)

As to participant 3, he stated that:

“Ket no natiliw me taysuspect'n, ketagresisting da ken tayitry da ngalumabankadagitiiofficersngaagimimplementi buy-bust operation.” (P3, Page 6, L.175-176)

(When we already caught the subject, he was resisting and tried to fight back the officers implementing the buy-bust operation.)

As to participant 4, he stated that:

“Kettinaexperience me tipinagimplementi RA 9165 ket very risky kasehanmo ammo no tiabilidadti subject, anatmangyarekanyam no guyudemsuna kasi mabalinnagalumabansynaramantiarmasna no adda man” (P4, Page 6, L.183-185)

(Our experience in implementing RA 9165 is very risky because you didn't know the ability of the subject, what will happen to him if you pull him, because he can fight with his weapon if he has one.)

The compromised personal and family security states the unprecedented threats and dangers not only to a police officer's life but also his family because of criminals caught have extensive power in their hands enabling them to retaliate on their detainer. Therefore, police officers should be educating their families about the risky of their job especially in drug operations which may they life be in danger not only to the personal lives but their family security as well to prevent them in danger or possible threats in their own lives.

This theme is supported by the study of Wasilweski, M. (2010), he stated that the law enforcement officers experienced many troubles and threat to their limb, lives, and even their careers. This is what police officers experience in the line of duty especially in anti-drug operation. Also, from the study of Anthony Didrick Castberg (2010), he stated that police frequently find themselves in volatile and dangerous situations where both their lives and the lives of unarmed civilians may be in danger. For instance, it is very challenging to handcuff a suspect who is resisting. A resisting suspect may be too strong for even two

officers to restrain. A civilian bystander may believe that police are acting brutally if there are multiple officers involved.

In addition, from the study of Corpuz and Delizo (2011), security measures are inevitable or necessary for attaining the goals and objective of a certain individual, group, or organization. It follows that when an individual or organization is exposed to hazards, their productivity is adversely affected. The role of security is to prevent or stop these hazards from causing unintentional or intentional damage to property, injury, or loss of life.

➤ *Theme 3: Thrilling*

The police officers feel excitement when conducting drug operations. In fact, they experienced excitement after making the arrest and filed a case against the subject. The subject's arrest brings relief, especially if the case is filed in an inquest or regular preliminary investigation. The police officers' best experiences are in this scenario, in which they rate the operation as successful. The fact that they were able to apprehend the drug suspect after extensive planning and operation preparation is gratifying. They hoped their efforts would result in a successful catch, so they took extra precautions. This is the supported proof that the police are very emotionally invested in their work.

As to participants 1, he stated that:

“Talaganga exciting kase different person, different operation, different experiences unlike kuma nu mestra ka kettiisuromtibigatketa,b,c,dtunnosumarunomngaklasemmanenketa,b,c,d. Nu drug operation gamin, sabalingataosabali jay experiences mosabalitmaammomngatao. (P1, Page 3, L.90-93)

(Exciting because different person, different operation, different experiences unlike if you are a teacher that in the morning is about a,b,c,d and tomorrow is about a,b,c,d again, In operation, different people, different experiences, and different people to meet, but the experiences of one person are unique; if they are the same, the experience becomes monotonous.)

As to participants 3, he stated that:

“Ket para kanyakti experience ko in hot pursuit operation ket excitement ken anaragsakngatiliwentay suspect ken pilaantimabalin a kasolabankanyanagapuiti damage or no ana man a violation tinaaramidna.” (P3, Page 6, L. 179-181)

(Well for me my experience in a hot pursuit operation, I'm in excite and happy to caught the perpetrator to file any charges against him for the damage incurred or whatever violation he does.)

These findings hold implications that the experiences of police officers can greatly impact their feelings. Based on the findings, job experiences help improve the psychological domain when preventing, detecting, arresting, and filling cases most often involving drug users. Specifically, positive feelings expand the scope of an individual's satisfaction and thus enhance police officer's involvement during buy-bust operation that promotes happiness. According to Zhai and Quinn (2014), the feeling of contentment and satisfaction of their job performance brings happiness to the personal and professional career.

The excitement depends on the performance or experience in accomplishing its mandated task. The police officers find themselves able to reveal their feelings within the police force about their varied experiences in the conduct of the operation. This has been defined as seeking varied, novel, complex and intense sensations and experiences and the willingness to take physically attach to their duty to give all dedication on their duties to make them feel within their selves what is the real sense of being a police officer. Moreover, the best part of the job is the experience of excitement and fulfillment after a successful

anti-drug operation. The feeling of overwhelming joy and contentment in their hearts knowing that all their hardships, efforts and sacrifices payed off.

The study's findings are influenced by the theory of experiential learning (Kolb, 1987), where knowledge is created through experience. The first stage of ELT, which is the "concrete experience," emphasizes personal involvement with people in various situations. At this stage, a person frequently bases their actions more on feelings than a problem. Through experience, police officers tend to rely more on their feelings about their job performance. Thus, the experiences during the conduct of an operation, along with their feelings of excitement, have an impact on their learning.

This is also supported by Job Performance Theory, which explains that employees with a higher job satisfaction score have higher job performance. Such means that the more satisfied people are in their work, the higher job satisfaction they have. Aziri (2011) argued that job satisfaction represents a feeling that appears as a result of the perception that jobs enable the material and psychological needs. The police officers' psychological condition is to arrest the drug suspect successfully.

A. Problems Encountered by Police Officers during Drug Operations

➤ *Theme 4: Impediment of Body Worn Camera*

The police officers first problem encountered during the anti-drug operation was how they affected in using body worn cameras. Police officers face this issue because they are unsure of whether it will become a full memory or be discharged. The use of body cameras is mandatory when operatives serve arrest and search warrants, adding that this also applies to warrantless arrests, such as the conduct of checkpoints and buy-bust operations, "as far as practicable." If it is not documented before, during, or after the operation, the case may be dismissed.

As to participant 3, he stated that:

"Ken ti mechanical problem ti Body Worn Camera kettayhantay ammo no full memory ban wennaogdischarged" (P3, Page 4, L. 123-124)

(Also, the mechanical problem of the Body Worn Camera's we do not know that it will become full memory or it will be discharged.)

As to participant 1, he stated that:

"Amman pay dejay pay timaysangakwati body worn kasemediyomasunog ka nukwaidjay no hanmonairecordtaypasamakidjay area of operation." (P1, Page 1, L.14-17)

(Yes, another problem of body worn camera because you can be charged if you did not record the activities on the area of operation.)

As to participant 2, he stated that:

"Ti body worn camera ti problem encountered ko kadetaket bulky, bulky makitam, Makita ti suspect ngaada body worn camera 'm which is mesa pagdoubt'anna apay adacamera 'm, mabalinisudapattay hidden camera kumangemmabalinngaubraenusarem nu regular law enforcement ngem nu during implementation of illegal drugs gamin ketnarigatngaillemngdetay camera ah ta dakkelunay." (P2, Page 3, L. 90-95)

(The problem in body worn that I encountered, it was bulky, was able to see, and easily see by the suspect, which it is one reason for the suspect to doubt about you, why you have a camera, so it is better to

have a hidden camera, but you can use the body worn, if its regular law enforcement but during the implementation of illegal drugs, it is kore difficult to hide the camera which is bulky.)

As to the unpredictable memory, discharged of the camera, the body worn camera should be regularly checked by the manufacturer of the camera to explain how to recognize if that body worn camera was full memory or not, to determine if it is functioning or not due to its unexpected deficiency so that the police officers will not experience any problems that were not anticipated to occur. Additionally, the body worn camera's large size or visible makes it too troublesome to use during anti-drug operations.

According to ShielaVae A. Hoylar(2021), Nearly four years after Kian delos Santos, a 17-year-old student who allegedly resisted but was captured on camera dying helplessly at the hands of our own law enforcement officers, the call for accountability and transparency in PNP operations continues to grow. In response, the Supreme Court issued its 29 June 2021 Resolution on July 9, 2021, approving A.M. No. 21-06-08-SC, also known as the Guidelines for the Use of Body-Worn Cameras During Warrant Execution. Law enforcement officials are required to record pertinent incidents when arrest and search warrants are carried out using at least two devices (one body-worn camera and one alternative recording device). Notably, officers must abide by the Rules even when making warrantless arrests, to the extent that it is practical. If body-worn cameras are not available, the police officers carrying out the warrant must file an ex parte motion and obtain the court's permission to use alternative recording devices before carrying it out. Once the arrest has been made, the cameras must be turned on and must remain on until the suspect has been taken to the closest jail or police station. Despite this, the Rules outline the following situations in which the devices may be turned off during any arrest or search.

➤ *Theme 5: Refuse to Witness*

The refusing and unwillingness of the barangay officials to testify against the target of the operation. The barangay official's participation is crucial to the process, especially when it comes to the inventory of confiscated drugs or paraphernalia. Making sure they can provide witnesses for the operation becomes the police officers' tricky problem. They were having trouble because the officials were reluctant to become involved in a difficult and complicated situation.

As to participant 1, he stated that:

“Timaysanganakuwakettaykastahaannakayatdejay barangay official tinagwitnessidjay inventory dagijay drug seized item, which isotnakadissandejaykaso. Isot requirements idjay section 21, kasetiipappapilitnaidiawan kano met isunaidi time of operation. Tipumpumay-akidikadagitay barangay official ipalpaliwanag ko nga they are not required under the law nga adda da during the drug buy bust operation. Ken adada pay dagijaymabutengngaagwitness kasi taynatiliwketkumbagakabagyannawennogayyemna, isupampamayaknukwaidininote ko dijaytapos I will inform the DILG kasi neglect ti duty da dijay.” (P1, Page 3, L.71-82)

(The one reason is that, the barangay official doesn't want to witness the inventory of the drug seized items which it is a requirement in the section 21 because he argued that he is not in the time of operation, what I did on the member of barangay official I explained to them that they are not required under the law, that they are not present during the buy bust operation. And also, there are witnesses that scared to be a witness because the one who arrested is family related to them or close friend. The thing I did, I will note it and I will inform the DILG because it is a neglect to their duty as barangay official.)

As to participant 2, he stated that:

“Ti mesa pay a problemangaminkettay barangay official hannakayatagwitness kasi ibaganangaawansunaidi conducting of buy-bust operation, where in fact talagaawan da kasi protprotektarantayti safety da, sakbayayabansudatonnopanagininventory'n.

Isudijayagkaproblemakamnukwan no pinaginVENTORY kasi agrefuse da as a witness ken handakayatagpirman jay inventory form.”(P2, Page 4, L.124-128)

(One problem is that the barangay official does not want to witness because he told us that he is not present on the conducting of buy-bust operation, where in fact he is not present because we are protecting their safety, then we will call them in the actual physical inventory. From that it is our encountered problem during the inventory because they refuse to witness and signed on the inventory form.)

The mandatory requirements of Section 21, Article II of RA 9165, which explicitly state that the inventory must be conducted in the presence of the accused or his attorney or representative, a representative of the DOJ, the media, and an elected public official, who shall be required to sign the copies of the inventory and be given a copy thereof, were obviously broken by the apprehending officers. While the arresting team did not strictly follow the procedure outlined in Section 21 of Article II of RA 9165 and it should go without saying that the IRR does not ipso facto render the seizure and custody over the items as void and invalid. Before such noncompliance can be said to fall under the purview of the provision, there must be evidence that these two (2) requirements were met that it must be emphasized that the prosecution must convincingly demonstrate that (a) there is a justifiable ground for non-compliance; and (b) the integrity and evidentiary value of the seized items have been properly preserved. The justifiable ground for non-compliance must also be established as a fact. The court is not permitted to make assumptions about these grounds' nature or existence.

In addition, the refusal on the part of the barangay official who is invited to witness the inventory would result in administrative liability and even imprisonment of 12 years and one day up to a maximum of twenty (20) years plus a fine Php 500, 000.

This is supported by the statement of Juancho Gallarde (2018), he stated that Barangay officials were cautioned against refusing to witness inventories of confiscated illegal drugs during buy-bust operations or conduct of search warrant. He also cited a case in Cebu wherein the entire group of barangay officials was suspended for refusal to witness in an inventory of confiscated illegal drugs and paraphernalia.

According to Molenmaker (2016), to promote cooperation, people often rely on the administration of sanctions. However, from previous research, they know that those in control of sanctions are generally reluctant to punish non cooperative choice behavior and prefer to reward cooperative choice behavior, consistent with the do-no-harm principle. Houser and colleagues (2005) also stated that people could become less cooperative when threatened with sanctions, and previous research suggests both intention and incentives underlie this effect. Demir (2017), argued that there are uncooperative witnesses because of the perceived intimidation or threat against them or their family members. Blood-related witnesses may feel anxious about testifying in court because they are unsure how their participation may affect them, and may risk their lives by speaking up and may expose their loved ones to intimidation, threats, retaliation, and reprisal. Lastly, Molenmaker, W.E., de Kwaadsteniet, E. & van Dijk, E. (2016). The impact of personal responsibility on the (un)willingness to punish non-cooperation and reward cooperation, organizational behavior and human decision processes.

B. Strategies utilized in implementing Republic Act No. 9165

➤ Theme 6: Compartmentalization

Fear of leakage of information of top officials to order to extreme compartmentalization of information. This strategy of police officers shall keep all the information about the operation, and shall be all treated as sensitive and confidentially to avoid the operation breakdown. As to important in restriction of some vital information it can lead it to the successfulness of the operation.

As to participant 1, he stated that:

“Kadamingaoperatibaketmaditiagibagatiimpormasyon, sakami lang agiabgantunnobriefing’ngapukadijay target wenna suspect, sika ket recorder usaremtyay body worn camera, sika ket arresting officer kasjaytapnomaiwasan tayo ti leakage ti information.” (P1, Page 1, L.25-28)

(For us in operatives it is prohibited to divulge information’s, we can divulge information only in briefing about the target person, you as recorder using body worn camera, you as an arresting officer to avoid leakage of information.)

As to participant 2, he stated that:

“A kas kunak, compartmentalization ti munangamaubra santo implementation, ketdapat some members ti operative’s ti pela makaammoti information tapnomaiwasanti leakage.” (P2, Page 1, L. 20-22)

(As I’ve said, compartmentalization is the first thing to do before the implementation, it should be some officers of the operatives knows the information in order to avoid leakage.)

Compartmentalization is the first strategy of police officers in implementing RA 9165, for them to prevent leakage of information specially in the planned operation. The information was only be disseminate in the briefing of the Team Leader prior to buy-bust operation. Limiting the disclosure of the relevant information is one of the best ways for the successfulness of drug operation, it is presumed that drug related cases is very rampant in the society that even the smallest cases can be connected to many different activities that is why limiting the information to disclose is important to prevent the leakage of information and to keep all the information secure for the betterness of the execution of the operation. Through compartmentalization of information to personnel involves in the operation it may lead to the success of the operation, and this is a must thing to do in the field of law enforcement, and most important thing to do is, it shall be inherent by the police officers what is the importance of limiting the disclosure of information and what are the benefits of this. In competence motivation theory, it involves the experience of believes in their competence motivation, the theory centers the idea that people are driven to engage in activities to develop or demonstrate their skills, if someone successfully perform a challenging task and receive praises to others then they will experience a belief in their competence in that achievement. Therefore, the competence motivation theory signifies also what was the participant of the study stated that in every operation the first thing to do is compartmentalization before implementing, the respondent of the study believe that, for the operation to be successful it shall be limited the disclosure of the relevant information to achieve the goal, for that reason as to his response it can be his motivation in every operation that he believes they can achieve all the desire outcome of the operation if they can execute what he stated.

This is supported by the study of Marie-Helen Mara (2017) she stated that, their practices of limited information distribution and existing extensive compartmentalization of information was served as impediments to information exchange between agencies in the intelligence community.

In addition to that, the study published by Harvard Law review (2013), this article challenges the standard account of that disconnect, which emphasizes the difficulties of apprehending and prosecuting offenders, and advances an alternative theory of leaking. The executive branch's "leakiness" is often taken to be a sign of organizational failure. The Article argues it is better understood as an adaptive response to external liabilities (such as the mistrust generated by presidential secret keeping and media manipulation) and internal pathologies (such as over classification and bureaucratic fragmentation) of the modern administrative state. The leak laws are so rarely enforced not only because it is hard to punish violators, but also because key institutional actors share overlapping interests in maintaining a permissive culture of classified information disclosures. Permissiveness does not entail anarchy, however, as a nuanced system of informal social controls has come to supplement, and all but supplant, the formal disciplinary scheme. In

detailing these claims, the Article maps the rich sociology of governmental leak regulation and explores a range of implications for executive power, national security, democracy, and the rule of law.

➤ *Theme 7: Balay Silangan*

Is an intervention congruent with the Dangerous Drugs Board (DDB) Regulation Number 2, Series of 2018 that aims to establish the guidelines for community involvement in reforming drug offenders of drug offenders into self-sufficient and law-abiding members of society. Balay Silangan is an offshoot of Bahay Pagbabago, a reformation center.

By allowing every institution in the community to be involved as part of the shared social and corporate responsibility in addressing the threat of illegal drug abuse, the Reformation Center or "BAHAY PAGBABAGO" operates on the spirit of volunteerism without expenses being incurred on the part of the patients as well as the government and its instrumentalities. It sustains its existence thru the support coming from the corporate community and civic spirited/ cause-oriented groups.

As to participant 2, he stated that:

“Ada dagiti program LGU ngakwaitibalaysilangan or ag undergo da iti community based, CBRP iti court, community based program kunanansadijaynga undergo da idjayagyan da tapnumarehab da, ada da pastor ngamakisaritakasta met maki join da dagiti different activities ayanti PNP in relation de toy core values ngamakakalikahanmapan da agtree planting coastal clean-up kasjay.”
(P2, Page 1-2, L. 23-28)

(There is a program of LGU which is the Bahay Silangan or they will undergo community-based program, CBRP in court, community-based program for them to be rehabilitated. There is a pastor who will give them preaching and by engaging in different activities of the PNP in relation to core values like tree planting and coastal clean-up.)

As to participant 3, he stated that:

“Strategies to utilized the implementing of RA 9165, a specially the programs given to the offenders like the Bahay Silangan, community-based programs.” (P3, Page 1, L.31-34)

As to participant 4, he stated that:

“Programs, like the Bahay Silangan wherein the offenders are being rehabilitate for them to cut the unlawful behavior and the using of illegal drugs.” (P4, Page 2, L. 35-37)

The BAHAY PAGBABAGO facility is specifically designed for surrendered drug personalities (who are not users/dependents) where they are given intervention, counselling, and livelihood with the end-in-view of helping them to become more productive and law-abiding citizens once they are reintroduced/reintegrated to the society.

Relative to this model and idea, the BALAY SILANGAN was conceptualized. This program shall also serve as an instrument for the reformation of drug personalities who avail of plea bargaining in light of the decision of the Supreme Court in the case of Estipona v. Judge Frank Lobrigo (GR No. 226679, 15 August 2017). This serves as an alternative intervention for drug personalities who are not eligible to be admitted in Treatment and Rehabilitation facilities supervised by the Department of Health (DOH).

CHAPTER FIVE

SUMMARY, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

This chapter reiterates the objectives or problems of the study, conclusions drawn from the findings, and recommendation based on the conclusions.

A. Summary

Based on the findings of the study the following themes were drawn. The different job experiences of the Police Officers found were challenging, compromised personal and family security, and thrilled. Moreover, the problems that were encountered are impediment of body worn camera and refusal to witness. Finally, the strategies utilized during their drug operations found were compartmentalization and the Balay Silangan Program which offers good and comfortable life for them.

B. Conclusion

The following conclusions and pedagogical implications were drawn based on the finding of the study. Challenging and thrilled were found as job experiences of police officers under Municipal Drug Enforcement Unit of Pasuquin, Ilocos Norte. This reflects the nature of work of uniformed men. It is challenging in way that their life is always at risk, they dealt and faced with different kinds of people from different economic and social status in life. However, their life and the life of their love ones were always compromised. It is given that the job of police officers is risky especially during drug operations or any man hunt operations wherein high value targets and dangerous individuals were involved which makes every life of skilled uniformed men is being compromised.

The study also shown the struggles encountered by the police officers which were impediment of body worn camera and refusal to witness. This reveals the feeling of not being safe, they are feeling threaten thus chose to refuse to witness. In addition, the lack knowledge about the law on who must be a witness.

The further found the strategies used by the police officers during their drug operations. One was compartmentalization. This shows that every information and operation must be kept high confidential to avoid leakages. The police officers crafted and implemented a program to cater the needs of drug users and pushers being arrested which the Balay Silangan Program. Balay Silangan Program offers a home for reformation. With this program, it reveals the innate tender, loving, care value of the policemen.

C. Recommendations

In light with the foregoing conclusions, the researchers offer the following suggestions:

- Findings of this study on the problems encountered, hidden camera may be utilized by the Philippine National Police in conducting buy bust operations instead of body worn camera used today due to its bulkiness. It will keep its purpose since it is tiny, thus it will not create suspicion on the suspect or bystander when worn.
- To the Barangay Officials, the researchers recommend that they may be given seminars on the Rights of Witness, the What and Who could be a witness especially during drug operations.
- To the Police Officers, the researchers suggest that they may enhance to imbibe the value of confidentiality of information to protect the families of the law enforcers, the law enforcers themselves and the subject of every operation and their families as well.

PROPOSED ACTION PLAN

“ENHANCING THE IMPLEMENTATION OF COMPREHENSIVE DANGEROUS DRUGS ACT OF 2002 AND SUPPRESSING THE PROBLEMS ENCOUNTERED DURING DRUG OPERATION”

A. STRATEGIES

The following are the strategies to be done in order to cope up to the struggle encountered by the police officers in conducting drug operations which are the following: Conduct sharing experiences, to create hidden camera, conduct personal dialogue seminars, to conduct seminars or programs in connection to the illegal use of drugs, and to make a drug awareness training simulation led by the PNP.

B. RATIONALE

This study is believed to be useful for the police officers, their family and the community. The findings of the study can be used by the agencies, particularly Philippine National Police, Local Government Unit and the Philippine Drug Enforcement Agency to be aware over the challenges and struggles the police officers' lives. Also, it would open up their consciousness towards positive and negative job experiences of their personnel's.

C. PURPOSE AND OBJECTIVES

To translate into action our commitment to the aims and principles of this case study, this study was implemented to investigate the job experiences of police officers, problems encountered and the strategies in implementing RA 9165 otherwise known as Comprehensive Dangerous Drugs Act of 2022. This plan is applicable to the future drug operations of the police officers and it can be improved.

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APPENDIX “A”: LETTER TO CONDUCT STUDY

DATA CENTER COLLEGE OF THE PHILIPPINES
COLLEGE OF CRIMINAL JUSTICE EDUCATION
Brgy. 1 San Lorenzo, R. Castro Ave.
Laoag City, Philippines

LETTER TO CONDUCT STUDY

September 26, 2022

VENCIOLY M. LUZANO
Police Major
Officer-in-Charge
Pasuquin Municipal Police Station
Ilocos Norte

P/Maj. Luzano:

Salutations!

The undersigned student who presently enrolled at Criminal Justice Education of the Data Center College of the Philippines, Laoag City, are currently conducting a study entitled “**Exploring the Job Experiences of the Police Officers under Municipal Drug Enforcement Unit in Implementing “Comprehensive Dangerous Drugs Act of 2002” (RA 9165) at Pasuquin, Ilocos Norte**”. This aims to understand the job experiences of police officers in conducting operations and the implementing of RA 9165 at Pasuquin, Ilocos Norte.

In this regard, the researchers are humbly asking permission from your good office to intend to conduct the study in your respected Municipal Police Station under Municipal Drug Enforcement Unit. The researchers would intend to hold an interview to at least five (5) selected Police Officers undergoing drug operations under the implementation of RA 9165.

Rest assured that all information obtained will observe strict confidentiality, that the researchers and the adviser will have the direct access of the data as it is used for research purposes only. Looking forward for your favorable response. Thank you and God bless!

Respectfully yours,

Aguillon
Aguillon, Ashley Nicole

APPENDIX “B”: Letter to the Respondent

DATA CENTER COLLEGE OF THE PHILIPPINES
COLLEGE OF CRIMINAL JUSTICE EDUCATION
Brgy. 1 San Lorenzo, R. Castro Ave.
Laoag City, Philippines

LETTER TO THE RESPONDENT

Dear Respondents,

Salutations!

The undersigned student who presently enrolled at Criminal Justice Education of the Data Center College of the Philippines, Laoag City, are currently conducting a study entitled **“Exploring the Job Experiences of the Police Officers under Municipal Drug Enforcement Unit in Implementing “Comprehensive Dangerous Drugs Act of 2002” (RA 9165) at Pasuquin, Ilocos Norte”**. This aims to understand the job experiences of police officers in conducting operations and the implementing of RA 9165 at Pasuquin, Ilocos Norte.

In this regard, may we respectfully request your cooperation towards the success of this study by answering our open-ended interview. Rest assured that your answers will be dealt with utmost confidentiality and will be used solely for research purposes.

Thank you and God bless.

Respectfully yours,

Aguilon, Ashley Nicole

Balabala, Mark Kevin

Calapao, Dianne Stephanie

DATA CENTER COLLEGE OF THE PHILIPPINES
COLLEGE OF CRIMINAL JUSTICE EDUCATION
Brgy. 1 San Lorenzo, R. Castro Ave.
Laoag City, Philippines

Interview guide questions:

1. What are the different job experiences of the Police officers in implementing “Comprehensive Dangerous Drugs Act of 2002” (RA 9165)?

a) Tell us about your job experiences when implementing the Comprehensive Dangerous Drug Act of 2002 RA 9165?

b) What is the most unforgettable job experience you have encountered?

c) From previous job experience did all your drug operation succeed?

d) Describe your own experience during/conducting Search Warrant?

e) Describe your own experience during Buy Bust-Operation?

f) Describe your own experience during hot pursuit operation?

g) Describe your own experience during the implementation of warrant of arrest to drug related suspect?

2. What are the problems encountered by the police officers during the conduct of Drug Operations?

a) What are the common problems you encountered during drug operations?

b) How did you overcome the problem during conduct of drug operation?

c) What is the most remarkable problem you encounter during drug operation?

3. What are the strategies utilized by the police officers under the Municipal Drug Enforcement Unit in implementing “Comprehensive Dangerous Drugs Act of 2002” (RA 9165) at PMPS?

CURRICULUM VITAE

AGUILLON, ASHLEY NICOLE
BRGY. 35 BIL-LOCA, CITY OF BATAAC

PERSONAL DATA

Age:	22
Civil Status:	Single
Citizenship:	Filipino
Religion:	Aglipayan
Birthdate:	July 10, 2000
Birthplace:	Bataac, Ilocos Norte
Gender:	Female
Height:	5'1"
Weight:	67 kgs.

EDUCATIONAL BACKGROUND

<i>Tertiary</i>	Data Center College of the Philippines Laoag City, Inc. Bachelor of Science in Criminology 2019-present
<i>Secondary SHS</i>	Data Center College of the Philippines Laoag City 2018-2019
<i>Secondary JHS</i>	Bataac Junior College 2016-2017

Elementary

Hilario Valdez Memorial Elementary School

2012-2013

“You will face many defeats in life, but never let yourself be defeated.”

CURRICULUM VITAE

BALABALA, MARK KEVIN
GAANG, CURRIMAO, ILOCOS NORTE

PERSONAL DATA

Age:	22
Civil Status:	Single
Citizenship:	Filipino
Religion:	Aglipayan
Birthdate:	March 22, 2000
Birthplace:	Currimao, Ilocos Norte
Gender:	Male
Height:	168 cm
Weight:	64 kgs.

EDUCATIONAL BACKGROUND

<i>Tertiary</i>	Data Center College of the Philippines Laoag City, Inc. Bachelor of Science in Criminology 2019-present
<i>Secondary SHS</i>	Currimao National High School 2018-2019
<i>Secondary JHS</i>	Currimao National High School 2016-2017
<i>Elementary</i>	Pias-Gaang Elementary School

2012-2013

“Everyday there’s a problem, but every second there’s always a HOPE.”

CURRICULUM VITAE

CALAPAO, DIANNE STEFHANIE
BRGY. 20-N COLO, CITY OF BATAAC, ILOCOOS NORTE

PERSONAL DATA

Age:	22
Civil Status:	Single
Citizenship:	Filipino
Religion:	Born Again
Birthdate:	September 16, 2000
Birthplace:	Bataac City, Ilocos Norte
Gender:	Female
Height:	5'4"
Weight:	60 kgs.

EDUCATIONAL BACKGROUND

<i>Tertiary</i>	Data Center College of the Philippines Laoag City, Inc. Bachelor of Science in Criminology 2019-present
<i>Secondary SHS</i>	Bataac Junior College 2018-2019
<i>Secondary JHS</i>	Bataac Junior College 2016-2017
<i>Elementary</i>	Colo-Mabaleng Elementary School 2012-2013

“If you want something you’ve never had, try to do something you’ve never done.”

CURRICULUM VITAE

FERMIN, KATE CHARISE O.
BRGY. 13 MAGLICUAN, PASUQUIN, ILCOS NORTE

PERSONAL DATA

Age:	22
Civil Status:	Single
Citizenship:	Filipino
Religion:	Church of Christ
Birthdate:	September 25, 2000
Birthplace:	Pasuquin, Ilocos Norte
Gender:	Female
Height:	5'3"
Weight:	68 kgs.

EDUCATIONAL BACKGROUND

<i>Tertiary</i>	Data Center College of the Philippines Laoag City, Inc. Bachelor of Science in Criminology 2019-present
<i>Secondary SHS</i>	Ilocos Norte Agricultural College 2018-2019
<i>Secondary JHS</i>	Ilocos Norte Agricultural College 2016-2017
<i>Elementary</i>	Pasuquin Gabaldon Elementary School 2012-2013

“If God is all you have, you have all you need.” John 14:8

CURRICULUM VITAE

LAGUNDINO, JAN MARCK KRISTIEN
BRGY. BADUANG, PAGUDPUD, ILOCOS NORTE

PERSONAL DATA

Age:	21
Civil Status:	Single
Citizenship:	Filipino
Religion:	Roman Catholic
Birthdate:	January 29, 2001
Birthplace:	Banguì, Ilocos Norte
Gender:	Male
Height:	5'8"
Weight:	90 kgs.

EDUCATIONAL BACKGROUND

<i>Tertiary</i>	Data Center College of the Philippines Laoag City, Inc. Bachelor of Science in Criminology 2019-present
<i>Secondary SHS</i>	Luzong National High School 2018-2019
<i>Secondary JHS</i>	Luzong National High School 2016-2017
<i>Elementary</i>	Luzong Elementary School 2012-2013

"It's never too late to be what you might've been."

CURRICULUM VITAE

MALACAS, JOHN MILLER
BRGY. BAYONG, BURGOS, ILOCOS NORTE

PERSONAL DATA

Age:	21
Civil Status:	Single
Citizenship:	Filipino
Religion:	Born Again
Birthdate:	August 28, 2001
Birthplace:	Banguì, Ilocos Norte
Gender:	Male
Height:	5'5"
Weight:	55 kgs.

EDUCATIONAL BACKGROUND

<i>Tertiary</i>	Data Center College of the Philippines Laoag City, Inc. Bachelor of Science in Criminology 2019-present
<i>Secondary SHS</i>	Burgos Agro-Industrial School 2018-2019
<i>Secondary JHS</i>	Burgos Agro-Industrial School 2016-2017
<i>Elementary</i>	Bayog Elementary School 2012-2013

“Don’t stop when your tired stop when you’re done.”

CURRICULUM VITAE

PASCUA, JOHN MILNARD
BRGY. ELIZABETH MARCOS, ILOCOS NORTE

PERSONAL DATA

Age:	22
Civil Status:	Single
Citizenship:	Filipino
Religion:	Roman Catholic
Birthdate:	July 1, 2000
Birthplace:	Marcos, Ilocos Norte
Gender:	Male
Height:	5'8"
Weight:	90 kgs.

EDUCATIONAL BACKGROUND

<i>Tertiary</i>	Data Center College of the Philippines Laoag City, Inc. Bachelor of Science in Criminology 2019-present
<i>Secondary SHS</i>	Marcos National High School 2018-2019
<i>Secondary JHS</i>	Santiago National High School 2016-2017
<i>Elementary</i>	Elizabeth Elementary School 2012-2013

“Just do whatever makes you happy.”

CURRICULUM VITAE

SACSAC, JOHN FERMAR L.
POBLACION 2, PAGUDPUD, ILOCOS NORTE

PERSONAL DATA

Age: 21
 Civil Status: Single
 Citizenship: Filipino
 Religion: I.F.I.
 Birthdate: May 1, 2001
 Birthplace: Bangui, Ilocos Norte
 Gender: Male
 Height: 167 cm
 Weight: 55kgs.

EDUCATIONAL BACKGROUND

Tertiary Data Center College of the Philippines Laoag City, Inc.
 Bachelor of Science in Criminology
 2019-present

Secondary SHS Saint Jude High School
 2018-2019

Secondary JHS Saint Jude High School
 2016-2017

Elementary Pagudpud Central Elementary School
 2012-2013

“If others can do, I can do better.”

CURRICULUM VITAE

SALVATERA, BLESSIE JOY
BARANGAY 54A, LAGUI-SAIL, LAOAG CITY, ILOCOS NORTE

PERSONAL DATA

Age:	21
Civil Status:	Single
Citizenship:	Filipino
Religion:	Roman Catholic
Birthdate:	June 24, 2001
Birthplace:	Laoag City, Ilocos Norte
Gender:	Female
Height:	5'1"
Weight:	51

EDUCATIONAL BACKGROUND

<i>Tertiary</i>	Data Center College of the Philippines Laoag City, Inc. Bachelor of Science in Criminology 2019-present
<i>Secondary SHS</i>	Ilocos Norte College of Arts 2018-2019
<i>Secondary JHS</i>	Ilocos Norte College of Arts 2016-2017
<i>Elementary</i>	Lagui-Sail Elementary School 2012-2013

“Let your mistakes be your strength.”